

Good artists copy, great artists steal: strategies for creative exploitation of the CHAMELEON harmonisation assistant

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents an experiment designed to investigate the influence of a creativity support tool on music creation. Twenty five participants were asked to harmonise two very similar melodies, the first on their own and the second while given the opportunity to interact with the CHAMELEON harmonisation assistant. CHAMELEON can offer a variety of solutions in a melodic harmonisation task by harmonising according to a number of idioms and/or their blends. Comparison between the produced harmonisations by the participants and their selection of favourite CHAMELEON examples indicated that the majority of them were directly influenced by the solutions offered by the system. Three strategies by which participants exploited CHAMELEON were identified: borrowing of full measures or long chord sequences, borrowing of one or more single chords and finally, adoption of general concepts existing in the CHAMELEON examples. We argue that these findings indicate that the system has the potential to stimulate and promote creative thinking.

1. INTRODUCTION

The increase of the available computational power in the last two decades has opened new possibilities for computational support of human creativity. The effect of such systems has already been studied in the context of various creative human activities such as poetry writing [1], creative design [2, 3] or general problem solving [4]. Music creation, in particular, constitutes a fruitful domain for application of such approaches. Recent works have discussed the usefulness of machine learning systems for autonomous and collaborative music generation [5] and have dealt with the problem of evaluating complex creative structures whereby multiple machines interact both with each other and with a number of people [6]. While autonomously creative agents in music are undoubtedly evolving taking advantage of the overall progress in machine learning methods and the increase of computational power, it could be argued that computational creativity assistants may have even more meaningful applications. An analogous example is the widespread use of Digital Audio Workstations

(DAWs), following the increase of computational power in the last decades, which facilitated the recording and audio production processes by professionals and amateurs alike. In a similar manner, machines that can contribute to the composition of the primary musical material may constitute a paradigm shift for music creation. In such a future scenario, the conception and processing of musical ideas may be the result of collaboration between humans and computers.

CHAMELEON is a computational melodic harmonisation assistant that can be used by human composers as a creativity support tool. It can harmonise a given melody according to a variety of harmonic idioms and/or their blends based on a generative implementation of Conceptual Blending theory and statistical learning techniques [7]. Thus, it can produce a number of diverge harmonic solutions to a melodic harmonisation task. The question that arises when such systems are available, concerns the way users may take advantage of it. Does it help them to become more creative and how this may be defined?

To address such questions, we designed a repeated measures type of experiment comprising two conditions. In the first one participants performed a simple melodic harmonisation, while in the second they interacted with CHAMELEON prior to harmonising a very similar melody. In previous analysis of the collected data we demonstrated that computational assistance by CHAMELEON resulted in an overall increase of the produced harmonic complexity (captured through computational metrics) in comparison to no computational support [8]. This rise of harmonic complexity was not justified by the minimal differences between the implied harmony of the two melodies and it was thus attributed to the influence of the system that helped participants become more explorative in comparison to their initial approaches. This, however, was only a general observation. In this paper we are trying to complement the above finding by looking at this experiment from a more qualitative perspective. The goal in this case is to decipher the individual strategies adopted by each participant when interacting with CHAMELEON and to show that the differentiation of the harmonisations in the computationally supported condition was indeed a direct effect of using the system. The following sections will describe the experimental design in detail and will discuss the strategies that seem to have been adopted by participants in their utilisation of CHAMELEON.

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2. METHOD

2.1 Experiment

As mentioned above, the experimental procedure comprised two phases in a repeated measures type of design. In phase one, twenty five musicians (13 male, 12 female, mean age: 24), either students from the School of Music Studies of the Aristotle University of Thessaloniki or professional composers, were asked to harmonise the melody of a Greek traditional folk song called ‘Menexedes kai Zoumboulia’ in minor mode (see Fig. 1) by placing chords at the positions indicated by arrows (i.e. harmonic rhythm was fixed). It was requested that satisfaction of personal preference should be the sole criterion for their harmonisation, without the need to necessarily conform to standard harmonic rules. Voice leading was not at the centre of this study therefore participants were advised to omit it in order to save time.

Figure 1: The two melodies used in the harmonisation task. The upper melody was employed in the simple harmonisation task whereas the lower one was used for the computationally-assisted harmonisation. Arrows indicate the requested harmonic rhythm.

In the second phase, the same participants were similarly asked to harmonise a melody of a folk lullaby from Southern Italy also in minor mode (see Fig 1). Folk melodies were selected for harmonisation in both experimental phases since their melodic simplicity is believed to offer a generally more loosely implied harmony, thus leaving more space for harmonic interpretations in comparison to more complex melodies. An inspection of Fig 1 reveals that the selected melodies of both phases were almost identical featuring very similar implied harmonies. Therefore the task for the two experimental conditions was equivalent but not identical. The directions regarding harmonic rhythm and voice leading were the same with phase one. This time, however, participants had additionally access to CHAMELEON and they were prompted to explore its capability to offer various harmonisations of this particular melody. After giving a short demonstration of CHAMELEON, the experimenter made clear that the extent to which participants should exploit the solutions offered by it for their own harmonisations would be totally up to them. It was particularly stressed that it would be fine to even completely ignore CHAMELEON’s output.

At this stage, CHAMELEON offered the possibility to choose among eight different harmonic styles:

- Bach chorales
- Jazz standards
- The Kostka-Payne corpus [9] of classical and romantic harmonic style (18th-19th century).

- 20th century whole-tone harmonisations
- Polyphonic songs from Epirus in minor pentatonic harmony.
- Fauxbourdon excerpts or short pieces (13th-14th centuries)
- Modal homophonic chorales.
- Organum excerpts or short pieces (11th-12th centuries).

The participants could also decide whether they wanted to introduce some tonal difference between the two selected styles (same styles/modes with tonal difference could be blended) in the case they opted for a harmonic blend. Pressing the ‘harmonise’ button on the online interface revealed the score of the requested harmonisation and gave the options to play it back and download it in a music xml format.

In both experimental phases, participants filled in a post-task questionnaire complemented by free-answer questions for the purposes of user-experience evaluation but these data are not presented here. Apart from filling in the post-task questionnaires, participants submitted their melodic harmonisation for each phase. For the computationally-assisted harmonisation task they were also given the option to upload up to four example harmonisations produced by CHAMELEON that they found interesting or influential for their own harmonisation.

2.2 Calculation of harmonic features

Given that participants were free to use any type of harmonic pallet, thus potentially avoiding tonal harmonic devices, harmonic content had to be captured using idiom-independent features of harmonic plurality. To this end, three different features based on the Pitch Class Profiles (PCPs), the General Chord Type (GCT) [10] and the isolated type component of GCTs (without root information) were extracted from each harmonisation. The PCP is the 12-dimensional vector that describes the percentages of pitch classes in the entire harmonisation (harmonic part without the melody). To obtain the complexity of a harmonisation based on its PCP, the Shannon Information Entropy (SIE) of this distribution was computed, allowing the representation of any harmonisation complexity through a single numerical value [11]. Greater SIE values indicate PCP distributions that are more uniform, which, in turn, indicates a richer variety of pitch content in the harmonisation. The plurality of harmonic content within a harmonisation was also quantified through the absolute number of GCT chords (unique root-type components) and chord types (isolated type component of the GCT). Therefore, each harmonisation was described by these three values, for each of which, higher values indicated more complex harmonisations.

3. RESULTS

Fig 2 presents the boxplots corresponding to the values of the three harmonic features described above for each of the two experimental tasks: the simple and the computationally supported melodic harmonisations. The evident

differences between the two conditions have been found statistically significant in previous work [8] signifying an increase in the overall complexity of the harmonisations produced by our participants when interacting with CHAMELEON. In Fig 3 the same feature values are presented for each of the participants. It is evident that with the exception of very few participants (no. 5, 9 and 15), the majority produced more complex harmonisations when computationally supported. A closer examination of the produced harmonisations is carried out to shed more light into how this increased complexity is explained at the level of each individual.

Figure 2: Boxplots of the three harmonic feature values for the two experimental conditions.

Figure 3: Values of the 3 harmonic features for each of the 25 participants in both experimental conditions.

The following analysis is based on the comparison between the computationally supported harmonisation for each participant and the selected CHAMELEON examples they uploaded. Since we had requested our participants to select the most interesting or influential examples, we now sought to identify signs of such potential influence. Four of the participants did not provide any favoured CHAMELEON harmonisation. Therefore this approach could not be applied to them since there was no way of attributing characteristics of their computationally supported harmonisations to a direct influence by CHAMELEON. One additional participant made almost identical harmonisations in the two conditions and finally for three of the participants it has not been possible to identify clear influences based on the examples they selected. Therefore, the following analysis concerns the seventeen remaining participants.

Table 1 presents the number of times that each of the provided harmonic idioms was selected by our participants ei-

Idiom	Pure	Part of a blend
Bach chor.	3	13
Jazz	6	17
Kostka-Payne	4	14
Whole-tone	1	2
Epirus	3	10
Fauxbourdon	2	5
Modal chor.	2	8
Organum	-	2

Table 1: Number of times each harmonic idiom was selected either on its own or as a part of a blend.

ther on its own or as part of a harmonic blend. This table shows that harmonic blends were favoured over harmonisations based on a pure idiom and that Bach chorales, Jazz and Kostka-Payne idioms were the most popular followed by Epirus and modal chorales.

The comparison between each participant’s uploaded examples and their produced harmonisations revealed three different types of influence. The first and most popular type of influence was the use of single chords that also appeared in the selected examples. An extension of this strategy was the borrowing of whole unchanged measures or small chord sequences from their favourite examples. Finally, a few participants embraced more general concepts which they utilised in their own harmonisations. Table 2 presents the number of participants that fall into each strategy category. Note that some participants utilised more than one of these practices.

Figures 4, 5 and 6 show some indicative examples that demonstrate the above. In Fig 4 it is shown how participant no. 21 borrowed the first four measures from the Kostka-Payne harmonisation and used them in the exact same way. Furthermore, measures 5 and 6 were evidently influenced by the corresponding measures of a blend between Bach chorales and modal chorales. In particular, there was an exchange between the 1st and 3rd chords of this four-chord sequence. Participant no.9 (Fig. 5), on the other hand, did not borrow unchanged measures but rather interestingly borrowed an abstract concept from one CHAMELEON example. Specifically, the harmonisation begins with a gradual increase of chord density in a similar fashion to measures 5-7 of the Epirus example. Finally, participant no. 5 (Fig. 6) has made use of all identified strategies presented in Table 2. In particular, apart from using unchanged chord sequences and a single chord appearing in CHAMELEON examples, she also adopted the overlap of melodic line by the inner voices evident in the Jazz Ionian - Jazz Lydian blend. For all the examples we also show the ‘Menexedes kai Zoumboulia’ harmonisation to demonstrate the difference from their initial solution on a very similar task.

4. DISCUSSION

This paper has presented the different creative strategies adopted by participants when interacting with a creativity support tool in the domain of music. The CHAMELEON

Menexedes participant 21

Lullaby participant 21

Kostka-Payne

Bach-Modal

Figure 4 shows musical scores for four pieces: Menexedes participant 21, Lullaby participant 21, Kostka-Payne, and Bach-Modal. The Lullaby and Kostka-Payne scores have red boxes highlighting specific chord sequences. The Lullaby score also has a green box highlighting another sequence. Dashed arrows point from the green box in Lullaby to the green box in Bach-Modal, and from the red box in Kostka-Payne to the red box in Lullaby.

Figure 4: The strategy of adopting unchanged chord sequences from the CHAMELEON examples. This example constitutes an extreme of this approach as most of the harmonisation comes from borrowing chord sequences with little processing. The computationally non-supported harmonisation of ‘Menexedes kai Zoumboulia’ is also shown to demonstrate the difference of solutions that were preferred between the two experimental conditions.

	Single chords	Sequences of chords	General concepts
Number of participants	14	6	3

Table 2: Categorisation of strategies for creative exploitation of CHAMELEON and the number of participants that adopted each one. Some participants utilised more than one of the presented strategies.

harmonisation assistant is capable of providing the user with a number of diverge solutions for the same melodic harmonisation problem. The primary question was whether access to this wealth of solutions would be able to influence the final harmonisation of the participants. In this work we elaborated on our previous general observation that most participants produced more complex harmonisations as a result of computational support compared to working on their own. Was this increase of complexity merely the result of a second attempt to a very similar task or could the influence of CHAMELEON be specifically identified? The comparison between the CHAMELEON examples that were favoured by each participant and his/her final harmonisation showed that at least seventeen out of our twenty five participants created harmonisations that borrowed elements directly from their selected examples. This indicates that to a smaller or greater extent these participants were influenced by the outputs of CHAMELEON for their own work.

It should be noted that even when the metrics of harmonic complexity (types of chords used and distribution of notes) indicate only a minimal difference between simple and computationally supported outcomes as in the case

Menexedes participant 9

Lullaby participant 9

Epirus

Figure 5 shows musical scores for three pieces: Menexedes participant 9, Lullaby participant 9, and Epirus. The Lullaby and Epirus scores have red boxes highlighting specific chord sequences. A dashed arrow points from the red box in Lullaby to the red box in Epirus.

Figure 5: This example demonstrates the more rare type of influence that was the adoption of a general concept rather than a specific harmonic sequence per se. Participant no. 9 introduces a gradual increase of the chord density in the opening of the piece in a manner that resembles the closing of one of his favoured harmonisations according to the Epirus style. Notice that this new feature is completely missing from the ‘Menexedes kai Zoumboulia’ harmonisation.

of participant no.21, the two harmonisations are actually functionally quite different. In addition, both presented case studies of participants no 5 and 9 show a decrease in complexity according to most metrics which again is a direct outcome of the system’s influence.

Having shown that in most cases there is a clearly traceable influence of CHAMELEON’s output on the harmonisations by participants, the question that arises is whether

Menexedes participant 5

Lullaby participant 5

Jazz Ionian - Jazz Lydian

Kostka-Payne - Kostka-Payne D7

Jazz - Kostka-Payne

Figure 6: This example demonstrates all three strategies combined. Participant no. 5 adopted both unchanged chord sequences, one single chord and a general concept. This was the overlap of the melodic line by the inner voices evident in the Jazz Ionian - Jazz Lydian blend. The computationally non-supported harmonisation of ‘Menexedes kai Zomboulia’ is also shown to demonstrate the difference of solutions that were preferred between the two experimental conditions. Note that some enharmonic misspelling that takes place in some of the chords in CHAMELEON output is adopted as such by participant no. 5.

Participant no. 3
excerpt from the Chameleon quartet

Violin I

Violin II

Viola

Violoncello

Figure 7: An excerpt of the work for string quartet by participant no.3 that was based on the melody of the ‘Lullaby from Southern Italy’ and suggestions by CHAMELEON.

interaction with the system can indeed promote creativity. Does increased outcome complexity combined with high preference manifest an increase of creative behaviour? It certainly seems to imply increased novelty (i.e., divergence from the most expected solution) combined with at least equal value as subjectively assessed by the creators themselves, both of which have been indicated as important constituent dimensions of creativity [12]. In addition, based on the identified strategies the answer could be that CHAMELEON’s use does provide potential for creativity enhancement but it does not guarantee it. Cutting and pasting unchanged complete measures or long chord sequences cannot be deemed a particularly creative behaviour. At the same time, however, participants were well aware that they could completely ignore CHAMELEON’s solutions while making their second harmonisation. The fact that some of them opted for borrowing complete measures means that they found them adequately interesting. Adopting full measures or even a complete solution by CHAMELEON may not be entirely creative but it can certainly be efficient and time saving in a case where a creative outcome

is not the primary objective (in music education, harmonising for a choir, etc.). Moreover, the most popular strategy was the borrowing of single chords which can help to enrich ones’ harmonic vocabulary and result in more explorative harmonic solutions. Finally, the rare strategy of utilising general concepts that appeared in an example by CHAMELEON is certainly the most creative of all and demonstrates the potential for creative exploitation of the system.

Six participants of this study proceeded in composing miniature works for a string quartet based on the primary harmonisation they created on the ‘Lullaby from Southern Italy’ while interacting with CHAMELEON. These works were presented in a concert under the theme of ‘Collaboration between humans and machines in music creation processes’ that was given at the School of Music Studies of the Aristotle University of Thessaloniki in February 2020. There the composers had the chance to briefly present to the audience the way by which they took advantage of the melodic harmonisation assistant in their creative process. An excerpt of one of these short quartets by participant

no.3 is shown in Fig. 7.

All things considered, CHAMELEON harmonisation assistant does not promote creative behaviour by default, but as with all tools, it depends on the way of use. To conclude with one of our participants' quote on computational support of music composition: '...the computer creates the possibilities among which a composer is free to select.'

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